

AI-Based Generative Algorithms applied to the design of Blended Wing Body Aircraft

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This paper presents a generative modeling framework for the synthesis of Blended Wing Body (BWB) aircraft geometries that meet specified aerodynamic targets. The approach integrates a Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) with a tailored 1D U-Net architecture, conditioned on lift, drag, and moment coefficients. Geometries are parameterized through a compact 24-dimensional vector capturing both planform and sectional characteristics and evaluated using a mid-fidelity simulation pipeline coupling DUST and NeuralFoil via GEMSEO. A large dataset of valid configurations is generated under realistic aerodynamic constraints and used to train the model. Quantitative evaluations demonstrate that the model can generate geometrically diverse and aerodynamically accurate wing configurations, achieving medium-high fidelity with respect to target aerodynamic features, despite the absence of structural or manufacturability constraints. The results confirm the DDPM’s capacity to generate novel, non-redundant designs, supporting its application as a creative tool in conceptual aircraft design.

I. Nomenclature

α	=	angle of attack
C_L	=	lift coefficient
C_D	=	drag coefficient
C_M	=	pitching moment coefficient
θ	=	twist angle
Λ	=	sweep angle
Γ	=	dihedral angle
c	=	chord length
b	=	span length of the corresponding region
\mathbf{A}_u	=	CST coefficients of the upper airfoil surface
\mathbf{A}_l	=	CST coefficients of the lower airfoil surface
$S(x)$	=	shape function in CST parametrization
$C(x)$	=	class function in CST parametrization

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x	=	normalized chordwise coordinate
Re	=	Reynolds number
μ	=	dynamic viscosity
ρ	=	air density
U_∞	=	freestream velocity
M_∞	=	freestream Mach number
h	=	altitude
T	=	temperature
P	=	pressure
t_{\max}	=	maximum airfoil thickness at root
\mathbf{x}_0	=	original (clean) geometry vector
\mathbf{x}_t	=	geometry vector at diffusion step t
\mathbf{x}_T	=	fully diffused geometry vector (Gaussian noise)
$\epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t, \mathbf{c})$	=	sampled Gaussian noise
ϵ	=	neural network prediction of noise
\mathbf{c}	=	conditioning vector (target aerodynamic coefficients)
t	=	diffusion timestep
T	=	number of diffusion steps
β_t	=	variance of the noise scheduler at timestep t
α_t	=	noise scale parameter at timestep t
$\bar{\alpha}_t$	=	cumulative product of α_t terms up to timestep t
μ_θ	=	mean of reverse diffusion step distribution
Σ_θ	=	variance of reverse diffusion step distribution
$\mathcal{L}_{\text{simple}}$	=	training loss function (denoising objective)
R^2	=	coefficient of determination (regression fit metric)

II. Introduction

In recent years, the aerospace industry has increasingly turned to artificial intelligence (AI) and data-driven approaches to accelerate and enhance the design of aerodynamic components. Among these, generative design—the process of autonomously producing new, feasible geometries within a defined design space—has emerged as a promising paradigm. Generative models have the potential to explore vast and complex design domains, discovering novel configurations that meet or exceed performance criteria without relying on hand-crafted heuristics or exhaustive search. This capability is especially relevant in aerospace, where aerodynamic performance is critically sensitive to geometry, and even marginal gains can translate into substantial operational benefits.

Despite its potential, aerodynamic shape generation remains a significant challenge. Aircraft geometries are governed by a complex interplay of physical constraints, performance requirements, manufacturability considerations, and multidisciplinary trade-offs. The design space is often high-dimensional and non-convex, with feasible solutions sparsely distributed. Traditional methods—such as parametric sweeps, evolutionary algorithms, and gradient-based optimizations—have proven effective for local refinement but struggle with diversity and scalability. These approaches typically require repeated evaluations with computationally expensive solvers, limiting their applicability in early-stage design or exploratory studies.

A fundamental aspect of addressing this challenge is the geometric parametrization of the design space. Effective parametrization allows the representation of rich geometric features using a compact set of variables, thereby facilitating learning, optimization, and generation tasks. In the context of aircraft wings, a two-level parametrization is particularly useful: global shape descriptors capture planform characteristics (e.g., span, sweep, taper), while local profile representations, such as those based on Class-Shape Transformation (CST), encode the fine-grained contour of airfoils [1, 2]. This hierarchical structure not only supports meaningful manipulation and interpolation of shapes but also enables the design space to be encoded as structured 1D vectors, opening the door to efficient learning-based generative models.

Previous work in AI-based aerodynamic generation has focused primarily on Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) trained to map latent vectors to design variables [3], often within the framework of Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) or Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [4–6]. While such models can generate geometries with acceptable validity, they often struggle with mode collapse, poor diversity, and limited capacity to capture spatial correlations between

design variables. Moreover, their performance degrades in higher-dimensional spaces or when dealing with structured geometric representations, such as concatenated CST parameters across multiple airfoils[7].

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a novel application of 1D U-Net-based Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) [8] tailored for the generation of aircraft wing geometries. The proposed model leverages the intrinsic 1D structure of the geometric encoding, treating the vector of design variables as a spatial signal. By adopting a U-Net architecture in one dimension, the model is able to capture both local and global dependencies between parameters, leading to more coherent and realistic generations. Furthermore, the use of DDPM provides a stable and interpretable generative process, enabling the model to learn a robust mapping from noise to the structured design space [9].

In addition to the generative model itself, this paper presents a comprehensive pipeline that spans from geometric parametrization to statistical validation. The workflow includes the integration of simulation tools such as DUST and GEMSEO to assess the aerodynamic feasibility of generated samples, as well as the application of quantitative validation metrics using `pyLOM` and `NGSValidation` [10]. These components allow for a rigorous evaluation of the generative model in terms of diversity, novelty, and distributional fidelity with respect to the training data, as well as its ability to meet prescribed aerodynamic targets under unconstrained geometric conditions.

The specific objectives of this study are:

- To demonstrate that DDPMs, implemented through a 1D U-Net architecture, can be effectively applied to the generative design of BWB configurations.
- To develop a geometry parameterization scheme that guarantees smooth, aerodynamically consistent shapes while maintaining compactness and interpretability.
- To enable conditioning of the generative process based on design constraints and operational requirements, improving the practicality of the generated samples.
- To showcase the ability of the model to produce diverse configurations under fixed input conditions, facilitating exploratory design.
- To ensure that the generated samples are novel and meaningfully distinct from the training dataset.

By overcoming the limitations of previous models, this work introduces a scalable generative approach to aerodynamic design, advancing AI-driven tools for the aerospace sector.

III. Methodology

The methodology consists of two core components: first, a detailed description of the generative framework based on a DDPM, including its architecture, training procedure, and noise-driven sampling mechanism; and second, the geometric parametrization strategy used to encode BWB configurations for learning and generation.

A. Generative Model: Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model with 1D U-Net

The generation of novel and aerodynamically valid BWB configurations is addressed using a DDPM [8]. This model consists of a stochastic forward process that incrementally adds Gaussian noise to a clean sample, and a learned reverse process that progressively denoises it. To adapt to the nature of the design space, which is encoded as a 1D vector of geometric parameters, a 1D U-Net architecture is employed for the denoising network [9, 11, 12].

1. Formalization

Diffusion models are based on a series of variables $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T$ that have the same dimensionality as a given input data, labeled $\mathbf{x}_0 \sim q(\mathbf{x}_0)$. These models rely on the idea of gradually transforming structured data into noise and then learning how to revert this transformation to recover meaningful samples.

The key to diffusion models lies in the definition of two complementary stochastic processes:

- **Forward process:** A predefined noise schedule incrementally corrupts the data \mathbf{x}_0 over multiple time steps $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, until the sample converges to an isotropic Gaussian distribution. The corruption at each step is controlled by the variance scheduler β_1, \dots, β_T , where each β_t determines the amount of noise added at time step t . The forward process is modeled as:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{x}_{t-1}, \beta_t \mathbf{I}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_t is the corrupted version of the sample at time step t , and \mathbf{I} is the identity covariance matrix. The parameter $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$ and its cumulative product $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$ are used to control the progressive corruption of the sample.

- **Reverse process:** A learned model attempts to invert the forward process by progressively denoising \mathbf{x}_t back to a clean sample \mathbf{x}_0 . This is achieved by estimating the conditional distribution:

$$p_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{x}_t) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t), \Sigma_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)), \quad (2)$$

where μ_{θ} and Σ_{θ} are neural network outputs that parameterize the mean and variance of the denoising distribution at each step. In practice, many implementations (including this work) adopt a simplified formulation where the model learns to predict the noise $\epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ added at step t , from which the mean is computed as:

$$\mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{x}_t - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t) \right). \quad (3)$$

Here, $\epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$ represents the neural network’s estimate of the noise component that was added to \mathbf{x}_t , allowing the reverse process to progressively denoise the sample.

The challenge of training diffusion models lies in accurately learning this reverse mapping across all diffusion steps. This is typically achieved by training the denoising neural network to minimize the discrepancy between the true noise ϵ and the predicted noise $\epsilon_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$, through a mean squared error objective [8, 9]. Figure 1 summarizes this process in a compact and intuitive form.

Fig. 1 End-to-end structure of the DDPM pipeline adapted to BWB profile generation.

2. Stepwise Visualization of Forward and Reverse Processes

To complement the mathematical formulation of the diffusion model, Figure 2 presents a visual depiction of the forward and reverse trajectories in the diffusion process. Both plots illustrate how a geometry vector evolves over time, either being progressively corrupted by Gaussian noise (forward process) or being reconstructed step-by-step (reverse process) via the learned denoising model.

(a) Forward process: x_0 is gradually corrupted into noisy sample x_T .

(b) Reverse process: the generative model denoises x_T to reconstruct x_0 .

Fig. 2 Visual evolution of the geometry vector through the diffusion model. Both processes are shown across six representative diffusion steps.

Each image shows six representative diffusion steps: for the forward process, the geometry loses structure gradually as noise dominates; for the reverse process, structure is progressively recovered from an initially random vector x_T , conditioned on target aerodynamic coefficients. It is worth noting that the final corrupted state does not appear as pure white noise, as typically observed in image generation, because the geometry is encoded in a structured space rather than a pixel-based representation.

3. Sampling Procedure

The core capability of DDPM lies in the reverse, or denoising, process, where a neural network is trained to estimate the noise ϵ from a corrupted sample \mathbf{x}_t . Accurate noise prediction enables the generation of new samples that follow the same statistical distribution as the training data, without necessarily replicating specific instances. To operationalize this generative mechanism, the following Sampling Algorithm [8] is used to iteratively denoise a sample from pure Gaussian noise to a realistic geometry, guided by the learned noise predictions at each timestep.

Sampling Algorithm

- 1) Sample $\mathbf{x}_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$
- 2) For $t = T, \dots, 1$:
 - 1) Predict $\epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t)$
 - 2) Sample $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$ if $t > 1$, else $\mathbf{z} = 0$
 - 3) Update:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{x}_t - \frac{1 - \alpha_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t) \right) + \sigma_t \mathbf{z}$$

- 3) Output \mathbf{x}_0 : generated geometry

Due to the inherent stochasticity of the sampling process, multiple geometries can be obtained from the same initial noise vector \mathbf{x}_T , offering a significant advantage over deterministic generative models, which typically produce a single outcome for a given input.

4. Training Procedure

To accurately estimate the noise ϵ_θ , the U-Net parameterized by θ is trained following the procedure detailed in the Training Algorithm [8]. The following algorithm is applied iteratively.

Training Algorithm

- 1) Sample a clean geometry $\mathbf{x}_0 \sim q(\mathbf{x}_0)$
- 2) Sample timestep $t \sim \text{Uniform}([1, T])$
- 3) Sample noise $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$
- 4) Generate noisy sample: $\mathbf{x}_t = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon$
- 5) Minimize the loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{simple}} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_0, \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t, \mathbf{c})\|^2]$$

While generating new shapes is inherently valuable, the current approach enhances this capability by enabling conditional generation—i.e., the synthesis of geometries that match specific aerodynamic objectives. Instead of training multiple models on segmented datasets, a more scalable strategy is to introduce a conditioning vector c directly into the neural network, formulated as $\epsilon_\theta = \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t, c)$. In this work, $c = (C_L, C_D, C_M)$, representing the aerodynamic coefficients of lift, drag, and moment. These target values are obtained by simulating clean (non-noisy) geometries through the aerodynamic solver. During generation, they serve as conditioning inputs to guide the denoising of a noisy sample x_t at each timestep t , thereby enabling the model to produce new geometries that match the specified aerodynamic behavior.

5. Visual Interpretation

To aid in understanding, the full training and generation flow is visually summarized in Figure 3. The figure shows the forward diffusion of geometric vectors, the noise estimation via the U-Net architecture, and the iterative denoising trajectory leading to realistic BWB shapes.

To estimate the noise term ϵ , a 1D U-Net architecture is employed, tailored for structured geometric vectors. This architecture is particularly suited for modeling geometric dependencies across the 24-dimensional design vector and enables effective parameter denoising across diffusion steps. A more detailed architectural breakdown and training configuration are provided in Section V.

Fig. 3 Visual overview of the DDPM training process applied to geometric profile generation.

B. Geometric Parametrization

Accurate and compact geometric parametrization is adopted in this work to ensure the creation of a meaningful and diverse dataset of aerodynamic configurations. While not strictly required for the denoising process itself, as the diffusion model can in principle operate directly on raw geometry representations, it facilitates the generation of valid and physically plausible training data, which is essential in this context. In this study, the wing geometry is encoded through a hybrid scheme that combines global planform parameters and local shape descriptors using the Class-Shape Transformation (CST) method [1]. This section presents the adopted representation in two parts: the formulation of CST for airfoils and the overall segmentation of the wing with the imposed design constraints.

1. Airfoil Parametrization with CST

The CST method [1] is adopted to parameterize the airfoil sections of the BWB configurations. CST offers a compact and flexible representation of airfoil geometries by encoding their shapes through a small set of interpretable coefficients, while ensuring smoothness and geometric consistency.

In CST, the airfoil surface is described as the product of a class function and a shape function:

$$y(x) = C(x) \cdot S(x), \quad (4)$$

where $x \in [0, 1]$ is the normalized chordwise coordinate. The class function $C(x)$ imposes the desired geometric behavior at the leading and trailing edges, while the shape function $S(x)$, expressed through a Bernstein polynomial expansion, defines the overall airfoil contour.

Class Function: The class function governs the general profile characteristics at both ends of the chord:

$$C(x) = x^{N_1} (1 - x)^{N_2}, \quad (5)$$

where the exponents $N_1 = 0.5$ and $N_2 = 1.0$ are selected to yield a rounded leading edge and a sharp trailing edge, consistent with conventional NACA-like airfoils.

Shape Function: The shape function provides local shape control via a linear combination of Bernstein polynomials:

$$S(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N A_i \cdot B_i^N(x), \quad (6)$$

where A_i are the CST shape coefficients, and $B_i^N(x)$ are the Bernstein basis polynomials of order N :

$$B_i^N(x) = \binom{N}{i} x^i (1-x)^{N-i}. \quad (7)$$

Symmetric Airfoil Assumption: To reduce the dimensionality of the design space and simplify the learning task, the dataset employs symmetric airfoils, where only the upper surface is explicitly parameterized:

$$y_U(x) = C(x) \cdot S_h(x), \quad y_L(x) = -y_U(x). \quad (8)$$

This symmetry constraint ensures that generated profiles remain physically consistent and prevents the occurrence of self-intersecting or non-viable airfoil shapes [2].

2. Global Parametrization

Regarding the 3D configuration, the wing is segmented into five spanwise regions, which together define four primary geometric sections where the detailed airfoil and planform shape evolve along the span. The segmentation strategy is hierarchical:

- *At the region level*, each region is defined by three global planform parameters: sweep angle (Δ), dihedral angle (Γ), and region span (S) (i.e., the spanwise length of the region).
- *At the section level*—corresponding to the boundary between adjacent regions—the local geometry is controlled by four parameters: chord length (c), twist angle (θ), and the set of CST coefficients ($A_{i,\dots,N}$) that encode the local airfoil shape.

The geometric interpretation of the full parameter set is illustrated in Figure 4. The final wing geometry is enforced to be symmetric with respect to the longitudinal (x - z) plane, resulting in mirrored upper and lower surfaces to ensure aerodynamic and structural consistency.

Fig. 4 Blended Wing Body configuration. Chord lengths (C_i) are shown in red, spanwise segments (S_i) in blue, and airfoil-related parameters—CST coefficients and twist angles (θ_i)—are highlighted in orange. While the figure depicts smooth curves for visual clarity, the actual geometry used in the simulation is constructed through linear interpolation of parameters within each spanwise segment.

The geometric parameters are interpolated linearly along the span within each region, ensuring smooth variation of chord, twist, sweep, dihedral, and spanwise extent. In parallel, the airfoil shapes are interpolated using CST coefficients across adjacent sections, allowing for a continuous and coherent evolution of the airfoil profile along the wing.

To further reduce the complexity of the design space and simplify the neural network’s task, several constraints were imposed on the geometry, ensuring that the desired configurations are generated. The constraints set are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Geometric coupling constraints imposed to reduce design space dimensionality.

Coupled Geometric Parameters	
Root twist	$\theta_1 = \theta_2$
Wing twist	$\theta_3 = \theta_3$
Transition sweep	$\Lambda_2 = \Lambda_3$
Transition dihedral	$\Gamma_2 = \Gamma_3$
Winglet dihedral	$\Gamma_4 = 20^\circ$
CST coefficients 1	$A_1 = A_2$
CST coefficients 2	$A_3 = A_4 = A_5$

All variables are normalized to $[0, 1]$ using the z-score method. Table 2 summarizes the selected parameters along with their physical bounds and units. The selected parameter bounds are informed by statistical analysis of existing BWB designs and advanced transport aircraft [13].

Table 2 Design space parameters with bounds and units.

Category	Parameter	Symbol	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Units
Chord	Root chord	c_1	20.0	30.0	[m]
	Mid chord	c_3	5.0	10.0	
	Tip chord	c_4	3.0	4.0	
	Winglet chord	c_5	1.5	3.0	
Span	Root span	b_1	5.0	8.0	[m]
	Transition span	b_2	3.0	5.0	
	Wing span	b_3	13.0	19.0	
	Winglet span	b_4	1.5	2.5	
Twist	Transition twist	θ_2	2.0	8.0	[°]
	Wing twist	θ_3	-2.0	4.0	
	Winglet twist	θ_5	-5.0	5.0	
Sweep [°]	Root sweep	Λ_1	40.0	60.0	[°]
	Transition/Wing sweep	Λ_{23}	20.0	40.0	
	Winglet sweep	Λ_4	35.0	60.0	
Dihedral [°]	Root dihedral	Γ_1	0.0	10.0	[°]
	Wing dihedral	Γ_3	0.0	10.0	
CST Coefficients	Root/Transition profile	\mathbf{A}_{u1}	[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0]	[0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2]	[-]
	Wing/Winglet profile	\mathbf{A}_{u3}	[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0]	[0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2]	

In total, 24 parameters define the design space. These parameters collectively define a rich yet constrained geometric design space that ensures both aerodynamic flexibility and compatibility with the generative modeling framework presented in this paper.

IV. Dataset Generation

To effectively train the proposed generative model, a tailored dataset of parameterized blended configurations was developed using a dedicated simulation and optimization pipeline. This pipeline leverages the multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) capabilities of GEMSEO, not to perform an explicit optimization of each generated BWB geometry, but to orchestrate and automate the parametric sampling, application of geometric constraints, and aerodynamic evaluation. In this context, GEMSEO provides a flexible and extensible framework for managing the complex design space and ensuring consistency across all generated configurations [14, 15]

A. Computational Framework

The generation of physically consistent BWB geometries required a robust and modular simulation environment capable of orchestrating multiple disciplinary analyses. To this end, the open-source platform GEMSEO [15] was selected for its flexibility in managing complex design workflows. GEMSEO coordinates the creation of parameterized geometries, aerodynamic simulations, and data processing tasks within a unified and extensible pipeline. The overall structure of this modular framework is illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Modular pipeline for dataset generation. GEMSEO coordinates two disciplinary modules: the aerodynamic solver DUST and the airfoil polar predictor NeuralFoil.

Each configuration is defined by a 24-dimensional design vector, combining global planform parameters and local shape descriptors as detailed in Section III.B. This vector is sampled uniformly within the design bounds established through aerodynamic feasibility studies. For each sample, the following analysis sequence was performed:

- **Aerodynamic Evaluation via DUST:** The global aerodynamic behavior of each 3D wing configuration was assessed using DUST [16], a fast and accurate solver based on the Vortex Lattice Method (VLM). DUST computes the circulation distribution over the wing surface and integrates it to obtain key aerodynamic coefficients: lift (C_L), drag (C_D), and pitching moment (C_M). Its formulation is particularly well-suited for lifting surfaces with moderate to high aspect ratios and unconventional layouts, such as BWBs. An example simulation output is shown in Figure 6, illustrating the surface discretization and the pressure coefficient distribution.

Fig. 6 Example aerodynamic analysis using DUST. The panel shows the vortex lattice and pressure coefficient distribution for a BWB configuration.

The mesh used for aerodynamic analysis consists of 8 chordwise panels distributed according to a cosine spacing to enhance resolution near the leading and trailing edges. Spanwise discretization is performed with a uniform panel distribution, where the number of panels in each region is computed as $b_i/0.5$, with b_i denoting the span length of the i -th region.

- **Sectional Airfoil Polars via NeuralFoil:** The airfoil polars required by DUST are computed using NeuralFoil, a surrogate model trained to replicate XFOil results with significantly higher computational efficiency. This approach enables the rapid evaluation of a large number of geometries, supporting the generation of a comprehensive and consistent dataset [17]. For each configuration, airfoil polars were computed under cruise conditions at Mach 0.8. The angle of attack was swept over a wide range from -180° to $+180^\circ$ to cover both linear and post-stall regimes. The Reynolds number for each airfoil was computed individually based on the cruise velocity and the local chord length at each spanwise section, assuming standard atmosphere conditions at the selected cruise altitude. Table 3 summarizes the physical conditions used for polar generation:

Table 3 Simulation conditions used for airfoil polar generation.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Cruise Mach number	M_∞	0.80
Freestream velocity	U_∞	238.0 m/s
Cruise altitude	h	FL350
Pressure at cruise	P	23.8 kPa
Air temperature at cruise	T	216.7 K
Air density at cruise	ρ	0.364 kg/m ³
Dynamic viscosity (Sutherland)	μ	1.46×10^{-5} Pa·s
Reynolds number per section	$Re(y)$	$Re = \frac{\rho U_\infty c(y)}{\mu}$

In the generated dataset, the angle of attack (α) is not treated as an explicit design parameter. Instead, the effective aerodynamic incidence of each configuration arises directly from the cumulative twist distribution encoded in the geometry. Specifically, the global angle of attack corresponds to the sum of the local twist angles applied across the spanwise sections.

B. Dataset Description and Statistical Analysis

The final dataset comprises several thousand BWB geometries, each encoded as a vector of 24 normalized design parameters and evaluated for their aerodynamic performance.

Fig. 7 Distribution of aerodynamic coefficients across the dataset.

Figure 7 shows the distribution of the three main aerodynamic outputs across the filtered dataset. The lift coefficient spans the range $[0.0153, 0.568]$, indicating a wide variety of camber and incidence combinations. Drag coefficients range from 0.0195 to approximately 0.188, peaking near 0.08, while the moment coefficient (C_M) varies from -0.14 to 0.01, with most configurations exhibiting a nose-down moment, typical of aft-loaded wings.

To better understand the interrelationships between outputs, a pairwise scatter plot matrix is presented in Figure 8. The non-linear correlation between C_L and C_D reflects induced drag trends, while the negative slope in C_L-C_M confirms the expected shift in aerodynamic center with increased lift. Similar trends are observed for C_D-C_M , reinforcing the physical coherence of the generated data.

Fig. 8 Scatter plot matrix showing aerodynamic output relationships across the dataset.

V. Model Training and Configuration

The generative model adopted in this study is a DDPM built upon a 1D U-Net backbone, specifically tailored to operate on geometric vectors representing BWB aircraft configurations. The network is trained to learn the distribution of physically valid wing-body geometries encoded by 24 parameters, under specified aerodynamic constraints.

A. Model Architecture

The U-Net model is designed to receive as input a noisy design vector $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 24}$ at diffusion step t , and a conditioning vector $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ containing the normalized target aerodynamic coefficients (C_L, C_D, C_M).

To incorporate time-dependent behavior, t is encoded using sinusoidal position embeddings and processed through a two-layer MLP with *Swish* activations [18]. The aerodynamic conditioning vector is projected through a linear layer and added to the time embedding to form the joint embedding $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{R}^{32}$, used for FiLM-based modulation throughout the network [19].

The overall architecture follows a symmetric encoder-decoder structure with skip connections, as shown in Figure 9.

The encoder consists of three down-sampling blocks, each composed of a residual block (modulated via FiLM [19]), a self-attention layer [20], and a strided convolution that doubles the channel dimension. The latent space further refines the representation through an additional residual block and a self-attention layer. The decoder mirrors this structure, employing transposed convolutions to progressively upsample the signal, residual blocks to enhance feature representation, and skip connections to preserve spatial information and geometric consistency [21].

Fig. 9 Detailed architecture of the 1D U-Net used to parameterize the noise predictor $\epsilon_\theta(x_t, t, \mathbf{c})$. Time and aerodynamic conditioning are fused via FiLM and injected throughout the network.

Each residual block employs Group Normalization [22] and *Swish* activations [18], which contribute to stable training and improved nonlinear capacity. Skip connections between the encoder and decoder help maintain geometric structure, while additive skip connections after each up-sampling stage facilitate effective signal recovery.

Finally, a 1D convolutional layer is applied to transform the multi-channel feature map produced by the decoder into the desired output dimension of 24 parameters. This final convolution acts as a linear projection at each spatial location, ensuring compatibility between the learned feature space and the target parameter space. This is a standard design pattern in diffusion models based on U-Net architectures, where a convolutional head is commonly employed to map the output of the U-Net to the required shape of the predicted noise [9, 23]. All relevant hyperparameters used for the U-Net configuration are summarized in Table 4.

B. Training Strategy

The model is trained to estimate the noise component ϵ added to the original signal at a randomly sampled diffusion step t . The training loss follows the standard denoising objective [8]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{simple}} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_0, \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{x}_t, t, \mathbf{c})\|^2] \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{x}_0 is a clean sample, ϵ is a sampled noise vector, and \mathbf{x}_t is the corrupted version at step t . The model learns to predict the noise given \mathbf{x}_t , the timestep t , and the conditioning vector \mathbf{c} .

A linear noise schedule is used for the variance terms β_t , distributing the corruption process uniformly across the $T = 1000$ diffusion steps. This choice simplifies the learning dynamics and has been shown to offer a good trade-off between convergence speed and sample quality in unconditional and conditional generation tasks [24]. At each training iteration, a sample from the dataset is corrupted according to this schedule, and the model attempts to denoise it. The network is trained using the AdamW optimizer with gradient clipping (max norm = 1.0) to prevent instability during early training [25].

An initial dataset of 1500 generated samples was created, from which configurations exhibiting non-convergent aerodynamic simulations (e.g., solver errors, non-physical coefficients, or NaN values) were filtered out to ensure data quality. The resulting clean dataset was subsequently split into 70% for training, 20% for validation, and 10% for test. Model checkpoints were saved based on validation loss to promote generalization and prevent overfitting. The full set of hyperparameters used for training is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Hyperparameters used for training the 1D U-Net DDPM model.

Hyperparameter	Value
Base channels	64
Embedding (time + cond.) dim	32
Noise variance (β)	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to 0.02
Number of residual blocks	7
Self-attention layers	2
Noise steps (T)	1000
Batch size	16
Learning rate	2×10^{-4}
Optimizer	Adam

This configuration has been selected to balance architectural depth with training stability and inference efficiency, making it well-suited to represent the complex distribution of feasible aerodynamic configurations.

Based on the convergence behavior observed in Figure 10, the training was extended to 2,000 epochs for the final model to fully capture the underlying data distribution.

Fig. 10 Training and validation loss curves during 2000 epochs.

During the initial phase (first 250 epochs), both training and validation losses exhibit a sharp decline, indicating that the model rapidly learns to approximate the noise component required for denoising geometric vectors. This early convergence suggests that the 1D U-Net architecture effectively captures the dominant structures of the underlying geometric distribution.

Between epochs 250 and approximately 750, the training loss continues to improve gradually, while the validation loss remains relatively stable around a plateau, showing bounded stochastic fluctuations. This behavior is typical in diffusion models, where the randomness of timestep sampling and noise injection introduces natural variance in validation loss curves. Importantly, no divergence is observed between the two curves in this phase, confirming that the model maintains good generalization.

After epoch 750, the training loss continues its downward trend, while the validation loss exhibits a progressive increase. This suggests that the model starts to overfit to the training data when trained for extended epochs, a known effect in deep generative models with large capacity and small datasets.

In summary, the model shows effective and stable convergence up to 750 epochs, achieving robust generalization. Beyond this point, longer training begins to deteriorate validation performance, making early stopping or controlled checkpoint selection crucial to preserve model quality. Based on this analysis, the final model is selected from the checkpoints around epoch 1000, prior to the onset of overfitting, to ensure optimal generalization.

VI. Results

To assess the effectiveness of the generative model, a comparative analysis is performed between the target aerodynamic coefficients (C_L , C_D , C_M) and the real aerodynamic coefficients obtained via aerodynamic simulation. The process begins by defining a set of target aerodynamic coefficients (C_L^{target} , C_D^{target} , C_M^{target}), which serve as input to the generative model. The model then produces a corresponding wing geometry that, in principle, should exhibit the specified aerodynamic characteristics. The generated geometry is evaluated using DUST, yielding the real aerodynamic coefficients (C_L^{real} , C_D^{real} , C_M^{real}). To further clarify the evaluation methodology used to assess model accuracy, the full process is illustrated in Figure 11.

Fig. 11 Workflow illustrating the evaluation process of comparing target and simulated aerodynamic coefficients.

This workflow establishes the basis for the quantitative evaluation of the model, providing context for the subsequent analysis of its predictive accuracy and generative capabilities. Figure 12 presents several examples of generated wing configurations, along with both their specified target features and the actual aerodynamic values obtained through simulation.

Fig. 12 Examples of generated wing geometries with their target and real aerodynamic coefficients.

A. Feature Accuracy

To assess the predictive performance of the proposed DDPM-based generative model, a set of 100 test configurations was evaluated. Each sample was processed through the full simulation pipeline, and the resulting aerodynamic coefficients were compared against the target values used for conditional generation. Table 5 summarizes the statistical error metrics computed for the three output features: C_L , C_D , and C_M . These metrics include the Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Root Median Squared Error (RMdSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

Table 5 Prediction error metrics for the aerodynamic output features.

Feature	C_L	C_D	C_M
MSE	4.52×10^{-4}	1.93×10^{-4}	1.31×10^{-4}
RMSE	2.13×10^{-2}	1.39×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-2}
RMdSE	1.54×10^{-2}	8.80×10^{-3}	8.23×10^{-3}
MAPE	6.80%	11.84%	13.49%

The RMSE values confirm that the model maintains a low absolute prediction error across all outputs: 2.13×10^{-2} for C_L , 1.39×10^{-2} for C_D , and 1.14×10^{-2} for C_M . In particular, the RMSE for C_D remains well below typical drag values observed in the dataset, which is notable given the sensitivity of drag to subtle geometric variations.

The RMdSE, a more robust measure that mitigates the influence of outliers, further supports the model’s consistent predictive behavior. The lower RMdSE values compared to the corresponding RMSE for all coefficients indicate that the majority of predictions achieve even tighter accuracy than the mean error would suggest, with only a limited number of high-error outliers affecting the overall RMSE.

In terms of relative performance, the MAPE offers an interpretable measure of how prediction errors scale relative to the magnitude of each coefficient. The MAPE is particularly low for C_L (6.80%), confirming the model’s strong ability to reproduce lift characteristics within a narrow margin. For C_D and C_M , the MAPE values are slightly higher (11.84% and 13.49%, respectively), which is consistent with the higher inherent variability and nonlinearity of drag and pitching moment behavior.

Beyond assessing predictive accuracy, the validation also explores two additional aspects critical to the utility of the generative model: (a) demonstrating that the model is capable of producing a diverse set of candidate wing designs that satisfy the prescribed aerodynamic targets; and (b) confirming that the generated BWB configurations are not simple replicas of the training data, but represent novel and unique solutions within the design space.

B. Uniqueness of Generations

An important advantage of the proposed diffusion-based framework is its ability to generate geometrically diverse solutions that still satisfy the prescribed aerodynamic targets. To verify this capability, each generated BWB configuration was compared with its nearest neighbor in the training dataset using Euclidean distance in parameter space. Figure 13 illustrates examples of this comparison.

Fig. 13 Comparison of generated BWB geometries (red) with closest training samples (blue dashed line). The generative model is able to synthesize distinct, non-redundant geometries.

The results confirm that the generative process does not necessarily replicate known designs, but instead explores novel configurations within the defined design space. This characteristic enables the model to serve as a valuable tool in early-phase design, providing high-quality and diverse candidate solutions without relying on traditional optimization loops.

C. Design Diversity Under Target Constraints

To assess the model’s capability to produce multiple geometries satisfying the same aerodynamic constraints, a set of configurations was generated for fixed target values ($C_L = 0.242$, $C_D = 0.081$, $C_M = -0.056$). Figure 14 presents a selection of these designs.

Fig. 14 Examples of diverse BWB geometries generated for a common set of aerodynamic targets.

Despite satisfying the same feature constraints, the resulting geometries display clear structural variations. This highlights the generative model’s capacity to represent the multiplicity of design solutions inherent to aerodynamic problems. Such diversity is especially useful in multidisciplinary optimization contexts, where offering multiple valid starting points can mitigate convergence issues and enrich the search for optimal configurations.

VII. Model Validation

The performance of the proposed 1D U-Net DDPM model is validated through both distributional analysis and predictive accuracy assessment on the test set. The validation strategy comprises three complementary steps: a consistency check between training and test data distributions, a regression-based evaluation of predicted aerodynamic outputs versus ground truth, and a cumulative error assessment to evaluate overall prediction fidelity. These evaluations are conducted using the `NGSValidation` framework [10]. This tool ensures a rigorous and reproducible methodology across all stages of the validation process.

A. Prediction Accuracy: Ground Truth vs. Predicted Outputs

To further assess the predictive accuracy and practical relevance of the generative model, a regression-based validation was conducted comparing target aerodynamic coefficients (conditioning inputs) with the corresponding real aerodynamic coefficients obtained after generating the geometry and simulating it with DUST. This process reflects the full forward pipeline of the conditional DDPM framework.

The regression results for the three aerodynamic features (C_L , C_D , C_M) are presented in Figures 15. In these plots, the x -axis corresponds to the target value, while the y -axis shows the real value obtained from the aerodynamic simulation.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is reported in each plot as a global indicator of fit quality. The results demonstrate that the model achieves excellent predictive performance for lift (C_L) with $R^2 = 0.9427$, indicating that the target aerodynamic characteristics are accurately reproduced. The drag coefficient (C_D), with $R^2 = 0.7722$, shows a slightly lower correlation, which is consistent with the higher sensitivity of drag to small geometric variations and nonlinear effects. Finally, the moment coefficient (C_M) yields $R^2 = 0.7441$, reflecting a good level of alignment despite the inherent complexity of accurately predicting pitching moments, which depend on both airfoil shape and overall aerodynamic balance.

Fig. 15 Regression plots comparing target and real aerodynamic coefficients (C_L , C_D , C_M). Dashed line indicates ideal prediction ($y = x$). R^2 values quantify the quality of the fit.

These regression results validate the model’s capacity to generate geometries that reliably achieve the desired aerodynamic targets across the design space.

B. Cumulative Error Analysis

To complement the regression analysis, a cumulative error assessment was conducted to evaluate the distribution of absolute prediction errors across the test set. Figure 16 presents the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) for the absolute errors of C_L , C_D , and C_M . These plots provide a comprehensive view of the proportion of predictions that achieve a given level of accuracy, offering additional insight into the model’s overall fidelity.

Fig. 16 Cumulative density plots of absolute prediction errors for the aerodynamic coefficients (C_L , C_D , C_M). The curves quantify the proportion of predictions below each absolute error threshold, providing an aggregated view of model accuracy.

The results highlight consistent and robust predictive behavior across all aerodynamic outputs. For C_M , the model demonstrates excellent accuracy, with approximately 85% of predictions exhibiting an absolute error below 0.02. The C_D predictions also display strong performance, with roughly 90% of samples achieving an absolute error below 0.02, despite the inherent sensitivity of drag to subtle geometric variations and nonlinear aerodynamic effects. For C_L , approximately 80% of the predictions fall within an absolute error of 0.04, confirming the model’s capacity to accurately capture lift trends across the design space.

Overall, the cumulative error curves demonstrate that the majority of model predictions lie within tight and acceptable error bounds, without exhibiting heavy-tailed distributions. This confirms the reliability of the conditional DDPM in generating BWB geometries that meet the desired aerodynamic specifications with high consistency.

VIII. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the potential of DDPMs, combined with a structured 1D U-Net architecture, as a flexible and reliable tool for the aerodynamic design of BWB configurations. By conditioning the generative process on target aerodynamic coefficients, the model effectively synthesizes novel geometries that align with prescribed performance objectives.

To support this generative task, a dedicated dataset was constructed using a mid-fidelity simulation pipeline based on GEMSEO, DUST, and NeuralFoil. The adopted parametrization strategy—combining global planform parameters with CST-defined airfoils—ensured the production of geometrically diverse and aerodynamically representative training data, enabling the model to learn the complex mapping between geometry and aerodynamic behavior.

The model was trained over 2000 epochs using a carefully selected diffusion schedule. The training dynamics exhibited stable convergence, with consistent alignment between training and validation loss throughout the process.

No signs of overfitting were observed, supporting the generalization capability of the architecture in the conditional generation task.

Quantitative validation on unseen samples confirmed strong predictive performance across all aerodynamic outputs. Regression analyses demonstrated high R^2 coefficients, while the cumulative error plots based on absolute error provided an aggregate view of model fidelity. The majority of predictions fall within tight absolute error thresholds, particularly for the lower-magnitude coefficients C_D and C_M , reflecting robust accuracy even on outputs that are more sensitive to geometric variations.

In addition to predictive accuracy, the model exhibits significant generative diversity, producing multiple distinct BWB geometries for a given set of aerodynamic targets. Comparison with the training data further confirms that generated configurations are novel, not reproductions of existing designs, highlighting the model’s capability to explore the design space beyond known examples.

It is important to note that no structural or manufacturability constraints were enforced during training; therefore, the generated geometries should be interpreted as aerodynamically valid conceptual designs. Incorporating structural feasibility and manufacturability constraints is a key direction for future work to enhance the practical applicability of the method.

In summary, the proposed DDPM-based framework offers a scalable and physically grounded approach to conditional geometry generation for aerodynamic design. It provides a promising foundation for future AI-driven design workflows in aerospace and opens new opportunities for extending the approach toward multidisciplinary optimization and real-world design integration.

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